

MATERIAL SELECTION OF Z-FIBRE IN STITCHED COMPOSITES – EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL COMPARISON APPROACH

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SUMMARY

Strain energy release rates are measured and compared for laminated composites stitched with three different fibre materials – Carbon, Kevlar and Vectran. DCB test and FEM simulation are performed to evaluate the interlaminar fracture toughness. This paper proves that Vectran provides the toughest interlaminar reinforcement and is most suitable for Z-fibre application.

Keywords: Stitched Composites, Interlaminar Toughness, Vectran, Kevlar, Z-fibre

INTRODUCTION

There has been a vast amount of research work dedicated to stitched composites over these recent years [1-2], which all indicate that interlaminar fracture toughness is greatly increased by Z-fibre stitching. However, there is currently no report on material performance comparison of Z-fibre, which limits the fibre selection of stitched composites in further practical application. This paper presents both an experimental and analytical comparison approach by investigating the interlaminar toughness of laminated composites stitched by Carbon, Kevlar and Vectran fibres.

DCB TEST AND FEM SIMULATION

DCB tests were carried out on various stitch densities (SD) and thread thicknesses of Carbon, Kevlar and Vectran stitched CFRP laminates. FEM simulation is developed to model the fracture phenomena in the z-fibre vicinity, such as debonding from the in-plane layer, slack absorption, fibre bridging, and pull-put of the broken fibre [1]. The present FEM analytical model predicted the experiment results for several kinds of composites, including the load-displacement curves and Mode I strain energy release rates, reasonably well.

The results represent linear relationship of G_I and SD for Carbon, Kevlar and Vectran stitched laminates (Figure 1). This linear relationship is true for all thread thicknesses and is useful to obtain new G_I (given a different SD value) by extrapolation without

executing further tests. Interlaminar strengthening effect increases with increasing thread thickness, as well as with increasing SD. Vectran thread (500d) is compared to CF thread (610d) and Kevlar thread (600d) – both of comparable thicknesses [3]. Vectran 500d shows the highest G_I /SD ratio value of about 50% more than Kevlar and CF. Vectran 200d, despite having thinner thread thickness than Kevlar 400d, shows almost equivalent G_I against SD relationship with Kevlar 400d. It is also noted that, for both Vectran and Kevlar, the material thickness is almost directly proportional to the G_I /SD ratio value.

Figure 1: Effects of Z-Fibre Materials on G_I against SD curve.

CONCLUSION

This paper confirms, by both experimental and analytical methods, that stitched laminated composite has greater G_I than unstitched laminate. G_I also increases with thread thickness and stitch density. Vectran stitched composite exhibits 1.5 times higher G_I /SD value than Kevlar and CF-stitched laminates. It is concluded that Vectran is a better material choice for Z-fibre application.

References

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